

THE ECONOMIC ASPECT OF VEHICLE RELIABILITY AND DEPENDABILITY

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Annotation. This articleThe problem of reliability is related to forecasting. In the early stages of vehicle development, reliability assessment is required for specific operating conditions. The science of reliability studies the process of changing the quality of objects (accuracy, power, productivity, resource, etc.) over time.

Keywords and phrases.Reliability, design of vehicles, production of vehicles, efficiency of vehicles, technical condition, performance, technical condition indicators, duration of operation, resource, periodicity of maintenance, breakdown, failure, classification of failures, operating conditions, design, technological, operational disturbances, production disturbances, accidental disturbances, gradual disturbances, disturbances on demand, related disturbances, unrelated disturbances

At present, there are thousands of different types of vehicles in the economy. Therefore, increasing the reliability of vehicles is of great economic importance. The cost of maintenance and repair during operation is much higher than the initial cost of the vehicle. Solving the problem of reliability can save a lot of money. The task of reliability in the design, production and operation of technical development TVs is to ensure their ability to work in difficult conditions and in the event of an accident, to predict the technical condition, diagnostics and to find the most optimal (reasonable) design solutions. yadi. Probability theory, physicochemical mechanics, friction theory, wear, and machine dynamics and reliability are used in the study of this science. The science of reliability studies the laws of change in the quality of

technical devices and systems, and on its basis develops methods to increase their service life without damage at the lowest cost.

The specifics of reliability issues are:

- Time factor. Because during the operation of the vehicle changes in the initial parameters are assessed;
- Predicting the technical condition of the object in terms of maintaining its output parameters (quality indicators).

The problem of reliability is related to forecasting. In the early stages of vehicle development, reliability assessment is required for specific operating conditions. The science of reliability studies the process of changing the quality of objects (accuracy, power, productivity, resource, etc.) over time. However, it does not study the issues of achieving a certain level of performance. The science and reliability of reliability in motor transport is associated with the study of the physics of damage (wear, fatigue strength, corrosion). This includes durability, wear resistance, heat resistance, and so on. calculation methods will be developed and technological processes will be applied to ensure the required reliability of vehicles. The theoretical basis of the science of reliability is:

- a) Mathematical methods of reliability theory;
- b) The results of scientific research (object materials, physicochemical degradation, wear and tear of properties of fuels and lubricants; mechanical degradation of materials; changes in the surface layers of materials; chemical degradation processes in materials and h.k.). The results of research in these disciplines (resistance of materials, physicochemical mechanics, tribotechnics, corrosion of metals, wear of polymers, etc.) form the so-called "physics of fractures" in terms of reliability. Deformation physics studies irreversible processes that destroy the original properties of the material (part) in the operation of the TV. A key feature of such research is the construction of events over time. The laws of time in the physics of distortions serve as the basis for solving the basic problems of reliability. Equations and connections that evaluate the working processes of the vehicle, dynamic loads,

efficiency, power characteristics, etc. are necessary for the analysis and evaluation of changes in the initial performance of the vehicle, ie to solve the main task of reliability. The science of reliability studies the process of changing the quality parameters of machines by probabilistic methods, as well as the laws of wear and tear, the processes of production and operation (the latter determines the performance of the vehicle). The task of the science of reliability is to provide a method of calculation of the machine (element), provided that the required reliability is provided. The calculations must take into account the probable nature (characteristics) of the processes of decomposition of machine materials. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the issues of predicting the reliability and performance of the vehicle. The economic aspect of vehicle reliability

The need to assess and increase the level of reliability achieved must be addressed from an economic point of view, as the economy is the main criterion in solving the problem of reliability. In order to achieve the required level of reliability, the condition of obtaining the most comprehensive economic efficiency must be met, taking into account the costs of production and operation of vehicles and the efficiency of their use when comparing different options. The change in the overall economic efficiency over time in the operation of vehicles depends on two factors:

1. Expenditures on a new vehicle (design, production, testing, adjustment, transportation, etc.) - Q_u ; and operating costs (TCC, T, preventive measures) - Q_e (L).

2. $Q_u = Q_e$ - a negative number in the balance of efficiency.

3. Vehicle use (income) provides positive economic efficiency-benefits Winter (L). Over time, Winter (L) begins to grow as the vehicle becomes obsolete and the cost of restoring its lost performance increases. Over time, the growth rate of Winter (L) decreases, as the vehicle's stagnation in maintenance and repairs reduces its productivity. $Q(L) = \text{Winter}(L) \square Q_u(L)$

Therefore, the total efficiency line has the highest point and crosses the abscissa axis twice. When $Q(L)$ increases with $L \square L_{tq}, Q_u \square Q_e(L) \square Q_{ish}(L)$, where T_{tq} is the

cost recovery period, thousand km. Then the cost of production of the vehicle will be covered. From $L \leq L_{TK}$, the vehicle begins to benefit. However, the increase in profit decreases when operating costs reach $L \leq L_{Ox}$. Limited lifespan of the L_{Ox} vehicle. Here again we have the state $Q_u \leq Q_e(L) \leq \text{Winter}(L)$. In the case of $L > L_{Ox}$, the operating costs are greater than the efficiency obtained. The economically viable service life of the vehicle is L_e , $L_{max} < L_e < L_{Ox}$. Therefore, when choosing a vehicle option in terms of reliability, it is necessary to compare its production and operating costs with the efficiency obtained. The economic criterion is the main indicator when assessing the reliability of the vehicle.

Транспорт воситаси иқтисодий самарадорлигининг вақт бўйича ўзгариши: L_{TK} — транспорт воситасининг таннархини қоплаш масофаси, минг км; L_{Ox} — транспорт воситасининг чегаравий ҳолатигача ишлаш масофаси, минг км; L_{max} — энг юқори самарадорликка эришиладиган масофа, минг км; L_e — транспорт воситасидан фойдаланиш иқтисодий мақбул масофаси, минг км.